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Lotka's Law and Bioinformatics Research in India

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Abstract

The study aims to examine the validity of Lotka's law and authorship distribution to the research outcome of Indian bioinformatics research output indexed in the web of science during 2008-2017. This study has applied Lotka's law to assess authors' productivity pattern of bioinformatics literature and further Chi-square test and Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) goodness-of-fit test applied for testing of observed and expected author productivity data. A total of 8732 papers has been scattered in 1723 journals during the period were compiled from web of science database. Using 'straight count' of authors, a total of 3835 authors were identified and the Lotka's law was tested using K-S goodness-of-fit test and Chi-square test. The results indicate that the author productivity distribution of Lotka's law is applicable to bioinformatics literature, while applying K-S test and not applicable when the Chi-square test is employed. This study is significant, as there have been no such studies conducted in the area of Indian bioinformatics research output and it will definitely set a baseline for future studies on author productivity of bioinformatics research output.

Keywords: Bioinformatics, Chi-Square test, Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test, Lotka's Law, Web of Science.

1. Introduction

The computational methods for comparative analysis of genome data was referred as bioinformatics from the late 80s and this new branch has become an integral part for storage, retrieval and analysis of biological data since then (Hogeweg, 2011). Bioinformatics, in a broader sense, deals with the usage of computer science in solving biological problems. The recent years has seen enormous amount of data being generated at an unprecedented pace in the field of biology due to the fast growing technology. According to Lesk (2014) "the reduction in the cost of genome sequencing has made it possible to obtain data on almost

every species and this huge data needs to be analyzed for answering various biological questions ranging from the field of disease biology, developmental biology to evolutionary biology". The immensity and complexity of the biological data has helped the bioinformatics to take shape as separate field of study and without basic knowledge of bioinformatics tools modern biological research has become impossible.

India has experienced an extensive growth of research in bioinformatics in the past decades since 1960s. The field of bioinformatics has undergone significant evolution in India. The number of publications has been increasing significantly

during the years within the field of life science. The DBT, Government of India is primarily responsible for the extensive infrastructure and network that was initiated way back in 1980s for the spread of bioinformatics centres across India, and is being supported at 168 locations across the country. According to Krishnaswamy and Mohan (2016), "India was the first country to conceptualise and establish, during 1986-87, a national distributed bioinformatics network (BTISNET), which is now the largest in the world. Even as the term 'bioinformatics' was just coined, the DBT took a bold step in initiating the Biotechnology Information System Network".

Research evaluation of any organization is based on indicators of science and technology (S&T) activity. For research evaluation, bibliometrics and scientometrics tools were applied. It provides quantitative approach in science studies. The application of bibliometric laws such as Lotka's law of scientific productivity is the one of the areas of scientometric research. Previously a number of studies have been made in to describe scientific productivity in various branches of knowledge. These studies suggest that law of scientific productivity follows an inverse law of growth and measures the frequency of occurrence of scientific output.

2. Previous studies

Pao (1986) and Nicholls (1989) studied the validity of the law, who found that the Lotka model fitted the majority of the data sets studied. Barik and Jena (2021) verified whether the authors' productivity pattern of Library and Information Science (LIS) open access journals adheres to Lotka's inverse square law of scientific productivity. The validity of Lotka's law and author productivity in the field of Economic literature was conducted by Tunga (2021).

Again Tunga (2020) studied author productivity and the application of Lotka's law in the field of Horticulture. Radhika, Thanuskodi and Sudhakar (2020) analysed marine pollution literature retrieved from the Scopus database during 1989-2018. They tested the applicability of Lotka's law by applying Chi-Square test and confirmed that the law did not fit the marine pollution research output. The Lotka's law on authorship productivity of artificial intelligence literature has been tested by Ahmad and Batcha (2019) to confirm the applicability of the law. K-S test was applied and was found that the inverse square law of Lotka follows the data set. Kumar and Kumar (2019) studied the scientific productivity pattern of authors and applicability of Lotka's law in the field of astronomy and astrophysics research in India (2013-2017) retrieved from WoS.

Batcha (2018) studied the applicability of law on the dengue global publication. The study uses Lotka's empirical law of scientific productivity, and proved that the law didn't follow the data. Kumar (2018) examined the authorship pattern of 556 papers published in the Journal of Documentation and verified the Lotka's law by applying K-S test. Found that the law was applicable in LIS literature. Da Silva (2018) described that "the law cannot be dismissed after considering a massive sample of the number of publications of Brazilian researchers in journals listed on the SCImago Journal Rank and the Journal Citation Reports". Sharma and Chakravarty (2018) studied the research of LIS by the faculties of north Indian central universities (1978-2014). It was found that the Lotka's law was applicable to the data. Dhoble and Kumar (2017) made a study on the authorship pattern and applicability of Lotka's law in the mustard research output in India. The study applied Chi-square test to validate the data and

disclosed that collaboration of more number of authors per article dominates in publications activities in this research. Naqvi and Fatima (2017) analysed international business literature to study the applicability of Lotka's law. Further, K-S goodness of fit test and Chi square test were applied to compare and confirm the data set and found that, Lotka's law confirmed the author productivity distribution. A bibliography record of oncology research output in India (2005-2015) in WoS database covering 10,298 research items was evaluated by Muthukrishnan and Kumar (2017), to test the applicability of Lotka's law. It was found that oncology research output conformed particularly well to Lotka's law. Sudhler (2013) in his paper analysed research output and examined the law and found that the author distribution pattern didn't found suitable. Again he conducted a study on the application of the law in the author distribution appended in the IISc physics doctoral theses (Sudhler, 2010).

A number of studies on the validation of Lotka's law were available, but no studies on bioinformatics literature were found. Hence, this paper attempts to study the validity of Lotka's law in author distribution pattern of Indian bioinformatics literature.

3. Objectives

- i. To study the authorship pattern of bioinformatics research output
- ii. To examine the validity of Lotka's law
- iii. To apply Chi-square test and Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) goodness-of-fit test for testing of observed and expected author productivity data.

4. Methodology

The study was undertaken based on the

data downloaded from web of science database for the period 2008-2017 using the following search strategy.

TS= (("Bioinformatics" OR "Computational biology" OR "Biology, Computational" OR "Computational Molecular biology" OR "Biology, computational molecular" OR "Biologies, Computational Molecular" OR "Computational Molecular Biologies" OR "Molecular biology, computational" OR "Molecular Biologies, Computational" OR "Bio-informatics" OR "Bioinformatic" OR "Bio Informatics" OR "Bio- Informatic" OR "Sequence analysis" OR "Genomics")) AND CU= India AND PY = 2009-2018. Refined by: [excluding] Countries/territories: The key words used for searching was taken from MeSH (Medical Subject Headings). First author count is employed for the author counting. All the searched results are first saved in text files and then imported into Microsoft Excel latest version and Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 17.0 was used for analysis.

A total of 8732 journal articles scattered in 1723 journals have been contributed by 3835 authors during 2008-2017, were retrieved using "straight count of the authorship method". Goodness-of-fit test was done using K-S and Chi-square tests for the conformity of the Lotka's law by using SPSS and Excel software. The methods proposed by Pao (1985) was followed.

4.1 Lotka's law of author productivity

Lotka (1926) was the first to study the author productivity from empirical data and proposed an inverse square law relating to author's productivity distribution to understand the worth of authors in progress of a subject field. Lotka investigated the productivity patterns of authors in a sample data from physics and chemistry. The general

formula is:

$$x^n y = k \quad (1)$$

where, y is the frequency of authors making 'n' contributions each and 'k' is a constant

The Lotka's inverse square law can mathematically be written as:

$$g(x) = (6/p)(1/x^2), x=1,2,3,\dots \quad (2)$$

where, $g(x)$ is the proportion of authors making x contributions.

A generalised form of Lotka's law was presented by Bookstein (1976) as:

$$g(x) = kx^{-n}, x=1,2,3,4,\dots x_{\max}, k>0 \quad (3)$$

where $g(x)$ represents the fraction of authors publishing x articles; k and n are parameters to be estimated from the data; x_{\max} represents the maximum size or value of productivity variables x ; and n is usually ≥ 1 .

The procedure proposed by Pao (1985) is followed in studying the validity of the law:

a. Calculation of 'n'

In the first step, determine the value of 'n' which is to be calculated either by following using LLS regression method or by an equivalent formula.

$$n = \frac{N \cdot \sum XY - \sum X \cdot \sum Y}{N \cdot \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2} \quad (4)$$

where N = number of pairs of data considered $x = 1,2,3,\dots,x_{\max}$;

X = logarithm of articles (x) and Y = logarithm of authors (y).

b. Calculation of k

The value of k , which is the theoretical number of authors with a single article, is determined from the following formula:

$$k = \frac{1}{\sum_{x=1}^{p-1} 1/x^n + 1/(n-1)(p^{n-1}) + \frac{1}{2} p^n + n/24 \times (p-1)^{n+1}} \quad (5)$$

Here p is assumed to be 20 and n is the experimentally computed value of the exponent from the observed distribution. Once the value of n and k is determined, then using equation 3, determine the number of authors writing 1, 2, 3, ... x articles.

To verify the observed distribution of author productivity fits the estimated distribution, applying the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) goodness-of-fit test. The maximum difference between the real and estimated accumulated frequencies was calculated, and this value was then compared with the critical value (cv) obtained from the following equation:

$$\text{Critical Value (CV)} = 1.63 / \{ \sum y_x + (\sum y_x / 10) \}^{1/2}$$

$D = D_{\max} =$ Differences between the columns of the observed and expected cumulative frequencies = $\sum f(x) - \sum (y_x / \sum y_x)$.

5. Analysis and discussion

Calculation of parameter 'n'

Initially for the validation of the law is to determine the value of 'n' and is calculated by linear least square method by using the formula (4).

Table 1: Calculation of the parameter n

x	g(x)	ln(x)	ln(gx)	ln(x) * ln(gx)	ln(x) * ln(x)
1	3835	0	3.58	0	0
2	886	0.3	2.95	0.887	0.091
3	270	0.48	2.43	1.16	0.228
4	120	0.6	2.08	1.252	0.362
5	80	0.7	1.9	1.33	0.489
6	39	0.78	1.59	1.238	0.606
7	17	0.85	1.23	1.04	0.714
8	12	0.9	1.08	0.975	0.816
9	9	0.95	0.95	0.911	0.911
10	5	1	0.7	0.699	1
Total	5273	6.56	18.5	9.419	5.215

By substituting the values in the equation (4), the value of 'n' is calculated as:

$$n = \frac{N \cdot \sum XY - \sum X \cdot \sum Y}{N \cdot \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2}$$

$$n = -2.9$$

Calculation of value 'k'

The value of parameter 'n' is calculated as, $n = -2.9$

Substituting the given value of 'n', the value of 'k' is estimated from the table of

exponents given by Rousseau (1993) as, $k = 0.82$.

By replacing the value of 'n' and 'k' in Lotka's model equation $(x) = kx^{-n}$ and the values calculated are shown in the Table 2.

5.1 Application of K-S test

Coile (1977) suggests the K-S test for validating the law. For applying the K-S test, convert the observed and expected number of authors into fractional values, and take the difference between cumulative fractional values of observed and expected numbers as shown in table 2.

Table 2: K-S test on observed and expected distribution of authors

x	g(x)	FOF	CFOF	FEF	CFEF	DOECF
1	3835	0.721	0.721	0.82	0.82	0.099
2	886	0.167	0.887	0.11	0.93	0.043
3	270	0.051	0.938	0.034	0.964	0.026
4	120	0.023	0.961	0.015	0.978	0.018
5	80	0.015	0.976	0.008	0.986	0.011
6	39	0.007	0.983	0.005	0.991	0.008
7	17	0.003	0.986	0.003	0.994	0.008

x	g(x)	FOF	CFOF	FEF	CFEF	DOECF
8	12	0.002	0.988	0.002	0.996	0.007
9	9	0.002	0.99	0.001	0.997	0.007
10	5	0.001	0.991	0.001	0.998	0.007
11	7	0.001	0.992	0.001	0.999	0.007
12	10	0.002	0.994	0.001	0.999	0.005
13	4	0.001	0.995	0	1	0.005
14	6	0.001	0.996	0	1	0.004
15	3	0.001	0.997	0	1.001	0.004
16	1	0	0.997	0	1.001	0.004
17	2	0	0.997	0	1.001	0.004
18	2	0	0.998	0	1.001	0.004
19	2	0	0.998	0	1.001	0.004
20	2	0	0.998	0	1.002	0.003
24	2	0	0.999	0	1.002	0.003
26	1	0	0.999	0	1.002	0.003
28	1	0	0.999	0	1.002	0.003
29	2	0	0.999	0	1.002	0.002
47	2	0	1	0	1.002	0.002
59	1	0	1	0	1.002	0.002

where,

- g(x): Number of authors contributing x number of papers
- FOF: Fraction of observed frequency of authors
- CFOF: Cumulative fraction of observed frequency of authors
- FEF: Fraction of expected frequency of authors
- CFEF: Cumulative fraction of theoretical frequency of authors
- DOECF: Absolute difference of the observed and expected cumulative frequency of authors.

The maximum difference value, Dmax representing the maximum deviation is

identified as 0.026.

The value of 'n' and 'k' were calculated to be -2.90 and 0.82 respectively. The K- S goodness of fit test was conducted at 0.05 % level significance. The D_{max} value is 0.026 and the resulting critical value is 0.264. Since critical value is greater than D_{max} , we must fail to reject the null hypothesis that the distribution is not different from the distribution predicted by Lotka's law. Hence the Lotka law is applicable to the bioinformatics publications. Therefore, the author's productivity data on bioinformatics fit modified Lotka's law with the value $?? = -2.90$.

5.2 Application of Chi-square test

The details of the results and analysis are given in the table 3.

Table 3: Chi-Square test of observed and expected authors

x	fo	fe	fo-fe	(fo-fe) ²	Chi
1	3835	3835	0	0	0
2	886	886	0	0	0
3	270	376	-106	11236	30
4	120	205	-85	7225	35
5	80	128	-48	2304	18
6	39	87	-48	2304	26
7	17	63	-46	2116	34
8	12	47	-35	1225	26
9	9	37	-28	784	21
10	5	30	-25	625	21
11	7	24	-17	289	12
12	10	20	-10	100	5
13	4	17	-13	169	10
14	6	14	-8	64	5
15	3	13	-10	100	8
16	1	11	-10	100	9
17	2	10	-8	64	6
18	2	9	-7	49	5
19	2	8	-6	36	5
20	2	7	-5	25	4
24	2	5	-3	9	2
26	1	4	-3	9	2
28	1	3	-2	4	1
29	2	3	-1	1	0
47	2	1	1	1	1
59	1	1	0	0	0
Chi-Square					286.5

Where,

x = number of papers

fo = observed number of authors

fe = expected number of authors

To find out the suitability of Lotka's law in the observed author productivity distribution, compare the calculated Chi-square value obtained 286.25 with the critical value of Chi-square at 0.05 significance is 37.65. On comparing, it is found that the

calculated value of Chi-square is greater than the critical value and thus the Lotka's law does not fit in the observed given author productivity distribution of bioinformatics literature..

5.3 Graphical representation

The graphical representation of the author productivity data is shown in figure 1. The graph is plotted as the number of authors in X-axis and number of articles in the Y-axis.

Figure 1 : Plot of number of authors and number of articles

The study shows that the Lotka's law in its generalised form follow the author productivity distribution pattern prepared for the first authors while applying K-S test. The application of the statistical tests, Chi-square shows that the author productivity distribution pattern does not fit Lotka's law.

6. Findings

Lotka's law of author productivity is regarded as one of the classical laws of bibliometrics. The present study has showed that Lotka's generalised law is not applicable to bioinformatics literature. The K-S test and chi-square test were applied to verify the applicability of Lotka's law of scientific productivity.

- The study shows that the Lotka's law in its generalised form follow the author productivity distribution pattern prepared for the first authors while applying K-S test.
- While applying the Chi-square test, it was found that the calculated value of Chi-square is greater than the

critical value and thus the Lotka's law does not fit in the observed given author productivity distribution of bioinformatics literature.

- The productivity trend of authors of journal articles of bioinformatics found to be different while applying K-S test and Chi-square tests.

7. Conclusion

This study examines the validity of Lotka's law to author productivity distribution in the field of bioinformatics research in India, covered in the web of science database. A list of 8732 journals articles on various branches of bioinformatics research covered in 1723 journals during 2008-2017 was compiled for analysis. Using 'straight count' of authors, a total of 3835 personal authors were identified and the Lotka's law was tested using K- S goodness- of - fit test and Chi- square test. The results indicate that the author productivity distribution of Lotka's generalised inverse square law is applicable to bioinformatics literature, while applying K- S test and is not

fit when the Chi-square test is employed.

Lotka's law of scientific productivity has been widely tested in the LIS field over the last several decades, but the results of the studies are inconclusive due to varying methods employed by the researchers. This study finds that literature in the field of bioinformatics research shows different results in confirmation with the validity of the Lotka's law. As a result, Lotka's law can be used in bioinformatics research as a standardised means of measuring author publication productivity which will lead to findings that are comparable on many levels (department, institution, national levels), as suggested by Askew (2008) in LIS studies. The results of the study would be useful for researchers, scientists and policy makers in the country in the area of bioinformatics. This may be the pioneer study in the area of Indian bioinformatics research and it may trigger more such studies for the purpose of testing Lotka's law in the various branches of bioinformatics and computational biology discipline. Future research could be directed to authorship and productivity studies in bioinformatics on various institutions in the country and on different databases. This study is significant from the viewpoint of the growing research on bioinformatics as well as various scientometric studies in the field of LIS to identify the authorship pattern, collaboration trend and author productivity pattern of bioinformatics research output.

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Mapping of Global Research Output in Webometrics during 2011-2020 : a scientometric analysis

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Abstract

This study aims to investigate the research publications on webometrics from 2011 to 2020 indexed in Scopus at global, national, institutional, and author levels as no study is discovered to analyze the publications on Webometrics. Webometrics is a very trending area of research in the field of Library and Information Science that came into prominence at the beginning of the 21st century with the internet revolution and enormous research has been going on it since its inception. The bibliographic data of the publications in the period were retrieved from Scopus using suitable search terms, excluding the irrelevant subjects which, gave data of 1202 publications. This data has been analyzed using MS-Excel and visualized with the efficient tool visualization tool VOSViewer. The findings reveal that India is a leading nation in this field following China (1st) and the USA (2nd). The University of Wolverhampton is a prolific institution and a faculty of the same institution Professor Mike Thewall is the most cited author. Moreover, the trending areas of research discovered in recent years are altmetrics, big data, sentiment analysis, social media analysis, learning algorithms, game theory. As no study has been encountered to conduct any form of review using bibliometric or scientometric parameters, this study finds importance, novelty, and originality.

Keywords: Bibliometrics, Global Publications, Scientometrics, Trending topics, Webometric research.

1. Introduction

The term webometrics is coined from two words, "web" and "metric". The Web is defined as a hypermedia system that facilitates users to view and retrieve information from documents containing links. And metrics refer to the measurement. Specifically, webometrics is a broad area incorporating link analysis, web citation analysis, and a range of other web-based quantitative techniques. Webometrics was

developed during the mid-1990s concerning the quantitative aspects of information available on websites. This methodology was developed, taking the idea from bibliometrics (Arunachalam, Koumpis & Handschuh, 2018). Bjorneborn and Ingwersen redefined webometrics as a sub-field of Cybermetrics and shared ideas with Bibliometrics and Scientometrics (Bjorneborn & Ingwersen, 2004). Thelwall (2009) defined webometrics as "the study of web-based content with

primarily quantitative methods for social science research goals using techniques that are not specific to one field of study".

Bibliometric investigations investigate the prolific author, journal, institution, highly cited paper, collaboration network, authorship pattern, chronological growth of publications, and many more based on performance-and-citation related metrics, science mapping techniques, and cluster and network visualization tools. The former practices are based on traditional measurements while the latter practices are based on the web. Now, this study has been conducted in amalgamation with both the traditional and software-based tools and techniques.

2. Review of related literature

Verma and Devi (2016) analyzed the web content and design trends of Library websites of IIMs. The study was well-drafted using a proper checklist. This study revealed that only 7 IIMs out of 12 have a separate library website. Devi and Verma (2016) also compared the design and content features of North-Eastern University and Mizoram University using a structured checklist. This study revealed that NEHU scored the highest point of 59 out of 69 than that of MZU scoring 47. Verma and Brahma (2017) conducted a webometric analysis of library websites of national libraries in South Asia based on the number of web pages, link pages, web impact factor, internal and external web impact factor analysis. This study revealed a very extensive result for India because the national library of India leads the highest domain and page authority followed by the National Library of Afghanistan. Brahma and Verma (2018) also evaluated the websites of public libraries of India based on webometric parameters using open site explorer. This study revealed that the highest domain and page authority was

achieved by Khuda Baksh Oriental Public Library and National Library. Brahma and Verma (2018) evaluated the national library websites of BRICS countries based on domain and page authority, domain, and extensions. This study revealed that the National Library of China was at the top, followed by the National Library of Russia. Brahma and Verma (2018) evaluated the library websites of the top 25 NIRF (2017) ranking universities using the data extracted from open site explorer. The study revealed that IISc Bangalore topped the domain and the page authority category with 75 and 55, respectively, and also in the external web impact factor (11.67). Brahma, Verma, and Sinha (2019) evaluated the university library websites of North-East India based on domain, page authority, link to sites, spam scores, internal and external links. The study revealed that the web impact factor of Mizoram University ranked the top followed by NEHU and Nagaland University Library. Verma and Pathak (2020) evaluated the websites of research institutes by ICSSR using root domain authority, web pages, total links (external and internal), web impact factors. The analysis of this study revealed that out of 29 institutes 10 institutes had .org extension. Verma and Pathak (2021) analyzed the contents and design trends of the websites of the Indian Council of Social Science research institutes. The analysis of data revealed that 17 ICSSR research institutes used one English language and 4 research institutes have got updated their websites in the last three months. Brahma and Verma (2022) analysed the web content of National Libraries' websites in Asia. The study discovered National Library of Japan in the top position followed by Azerbaijan and Taiwan.

2.1 Research gap

The literature study gives a clear insight that although a lot of webometric analyses are

available over the web. But there is not a single bibliometric analysis on publications related to webometric research is not available. Searching different websites, using tools like Publish or Perish and Mendeley, extensive search has been conducted to discover the research publications related to the bibliometric analysis of webometric research but not a single paper has been encountered. So, this study is an attempt to fulfil this research gap and conduct a simple bibliometric analysis on webometric research publications.

3. Objectives

- i. To evaluate the year wise growth pattern of publications
- ii. To identify the prolific institutions
- iii. To identify the prolific authors, sources, and countries
- iv. To analyze the prominent keywords in webometric research

4. Methodology

The data is collected from the Scopus database, the most reliable and efficient database for conducting scientometric research (Borgohain et al. 2021). The following search strategy is used to retrieve the data in the Article Title-Abstract-Keywords box with a trial-and-error approach: (TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Web Content Analysis") OR ("Webometrics") OR ("Web Impact Factor") OR ("Link Analysis") OR ("HyperLink Analysis") OR ("Web site usability analysis") OR ("Web Navigation Analysis")) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2019) OROR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2011)). Here, the search operator "OR" is used to connect the keywords instead of the operator "AND" the former conjunction gives reliable search results as it incorporates a broad coverage of relevant papers without leaving

important and related papers which in turn improves the accuracy and precision of the analysis. This yields reliable and efficient results which it won't be if the "AND" operator is used. Further, the irrelevant subject areas are filtered keeping the relevant keywords. The search resulted in 1202 papers. Further, these publications are fed into MS-Excel for statistical analysis. The ranking of the institution, author, source, and the country is done based on performance-and-citation-related metrics particularly the total citation count and total publications. Prominent keywords are ranked based on the frequency of occurrences. The overlay visualization of keywords to reveal the trending areas of research is done with VOSviewer (van Eck and Waltman, 2010). The figure so created is generated using the normalization method of "Association Strength" in the software.

5. Scope of the study

As mentioned in the title, the study has been designed to analyze the publications from 2011 to 2020. A decade of time frame is sufficient enough for conducting a bibliometric or scientometric analysis. So, these years are selected. Moreover, in these years the number of publications has increased manifold. Further, the study has been limited to publications indexed in Scopus only because as evident in many studies, Scopus is a very efficient and reliable database for conducting a bibliometric or scientometric analysis.

6. Results

6.1 Chronological growth pattern of publications

The number of publications has decreased from the starting year of the study from 2011 onwards as shown in figure 1. The growth of a number of publications is not consistent as evident from the figure which

also reveals a downward growth trend on mere observation. The highest number of publications (187) is observed in the year 2012 and lowest (88) in the year 2018 which accounts for 15.56% and 7.32% share in total publications. A total of 1202 publications are discovered with average publications of 120.2 per year.

Figure 1: Chronological growth pattern of publications

6.2 Prolific institutions

Table 1: Top 10 most productive institutions

Name of Institution	Number of Publications
University of Wolverhampton	47
Yeungnam University	46
Universidad de la costa	26
Kyoto university	22
Dalian University of Technology	20
Peking university	18
University of California	17
Pennsylvania State university	16
National Chiao Tung university	14
Renmin University of China	14

Table 1 has listed the top 10 most productive affiliations in Webometric research from 2011 to 2020. Institutes with at least 14 or more publications are incorporated into the list. The distribution publications in the top 10 institutions are highly skewed as the top 5 of them have 20 or more publications and following those in the list had as low as 14 papers. These top 10 institutions have produced 240 papers in total which accounts for 19.97% of papers in cumulative publications. The University of Wolverhampton, U.K. has recorded a maximum number of publications (47) followed by Yeungnam University (46) and the least in the top 10 affiliation list is Renmin University of China with 14 publications.

6.3 Prolific authors

Table 2: Top 10 most prolific authors in webometric research during 2011 to 2020

Name of the author	Total Publications	Total Citations	CPP*
HW Park	35	655	18.71
Mike Thelwall	31	1289	41.58
Y Zhao	17	122	7.18
M Samuel-Torres	10	111	11.1
L Vaughan	10	158	15.8
A Vilorio	10	111	11.1
IF Aguillo	9	238	26.44
X Zhang	9	328	36.44
F Danesh	8	15	1.86
K Kousha	8	335	41.88

*CPP=Citations per Paper

Table 2 has listed the top 10 most prolific authors based on two metrics namely, number of publications and citations. Authors with at least 8 or more papers are on this list. The distribution of papers in this list is also very skewed as authors in the top 2 have as high as 35 papers while from the 3rd author the number of publications gets as low as 17 and till 10th author it gets to 8 papers. These top

authors produced as many as 147 papers accounting for a 12.23% share in cumulative papers. For ranking the productivity, total publications were used as the medium. But the impact of an author in the field is revealed with citations and more accurately by citations per paper. Considering the number of publications HW Park of Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology is at the top with 35 publications, but if the impact

based on citation is taken into account Mike Thelwall of the University of Wolverhampton, U.K. is at the top with 1289 citations. Another parameter for identifying the impactful author is citations per paper (CPP) which supports the finding for Mike Thelwall and K Kousha with values of 41.58 and 41.88 respectively which are too close. In all, Mike Thelwall, a pioneer in webometric research is the most impactful author in the field.

6.4 Prolific sources

Table 3: Top 10 prolific sources in webometrics research during 2011 to 2020

Name of the source	Total Publications	Total Citations	CPP*
Lecture Notes in Computer Science	73	536	7.34
Scientometrics	47	1415	30.11
Library Philosophy and Practice	25	39	1.56
ACM International Conference Proceeding Series	23	122	5.3
Communications in Computer and Information Science	21	43	2.05
Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing	20	36	1.8
CEUR Workshop Proceedings	15	7	0.47
International Conference on Information and Knowledge Management, Proceedings	13	330	25.39
Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology	11	448	40.73
DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology	10	49	4.9
Electronic Library	10	64	6.4

*CPP=Citations per Paper

Table 3 has listed the most prolific sources in webometric research during the period taken for study. These are listed based on a number of publications and citations. Sources with at least 10 or more publications are included here. The sources produced a total of 268 papers accounting for 22.3% in cumulative publications. Again, very uneven distribution in the number of papers is observed in the list from the top to bottom. From the 3rd source, the number of publications has down to 25 from 47 in its preceding journal. As evident, Lecture Notes in Computer Science is the most productive source with 73 publications followed by Scientometrics, a leading journal in the field of Library and Information Science publishing original research articles with 47 publications and recorded top in the list as per the impact of the sources are considered with 1415 citations in the period. Again, CPP is considered the highest is for the Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology (40.73) followed by the Scientometrics journal (30.11).

6.5 Prolific countries

Table 4: Top 10 most productive nations in webometric research during the period 2011 to 2020

Country	Total Publications
China	637
USA	561
India	254
UK	196
Spain	170
South Korea	152
Japan	133
Iran	125
Germany	73
Italy	73

Table 4 has presented the top 10 productive countries based on the total number of publications. A country with a minimum of 73 publications is listed in the table. These top countries produced a total of 2374 papers including the collaborating papers too. China and the USA the two leading technology giants in the world are in the first and second positions with 637 and 561 publications respectively. It is a good sign that India is in the third position with 254 publications, keeping behind the developed countries like the UK, Spain, South Korea, Japan, Germany, and Italy.

6.6 Prominent keywords and trending topics

Table 5: Top 10 most occurring keywords in papers on webometric research during 2011 to 2020

Keywords	Frequency
link analysis	378
websites	165
social networking (online)	136
search engines	113
data mining	104
webometrics	103
information retrieval	79
algorithms	69
world wide web	66
hypertext systems	61

Analysis of keywords is of great importance in a peculiar bibliometric study as it gives an overview of research areas in a discipline. Table 5 has showed the top 10 most

frequently occurring keywords based on the frequency of occurrence. A keyword with a minimum of 61 occurrences is included in the list. As evident from the table, link analysis is the highest occurring keyword with a frequency of 378 followed by websites with 165. Besides keywords like data mining (104), algorithms (69), hypertext systems (61) are also observed though these are not directly related to webometric research.

Figure 2 was created using VOSViewer with 334 total connected keywords with a minimum number of occurrences of each keyword as 5. The figure depicts the variation of colour from violet to yellow. Each circle in the figure with a specific color represents a

keyword. The size of the circle is directly proportional to the number of occurrences of the keyword and the curved lines connecting those represent the co-occurrence of them. The keywords reflect the areas of research on a particular topic. From the internet, the research areas moved on to web search followed by social networking online as reflected by keywords like YouTube, Facebook, Twitter in light blue. From this, the research areas moved to web structure mining, data mining, HTML, hit counting, clustering algorithm. This is followed by the latest research areas like altmetrics, big data, learning algorithms, game theory, learning systems, online forums, sentiment analysis as reflected in by yellow color in the figure.

Figure 2: Overlay visualization of trending topics in webometric research

7. Major findings of the study

- The number of publications is decreasing from 2011 to 2020 onwards and the highest number of publications is recorded for the year 2012 and least in 2018.
- The University of Wolverhampton has a maximum number of publications (47) which is the most productive affiliation.
- HW Park, a Korean professor has the highest number of publications (35) while Mike Thelwall, a pioneer in

the field of webometric research is the most impactful author with 1289 citations for just 31 publications.

- Lecture Notes in Computer Science is the most productive source with 73 publications while Scientometrics journal is the most impactful journal with 1415 citations for 47 publications.
- China, the USA, and India are the leading nations in webometric research in the period taken for study with 637, 561, and 254 publications respectively.
- The prominent keywords are link analysis, websites, social networking (online) with a maximum number of occurrences.
- The trending areas of research are altmetrics, big data, learning algorithms, game theory, learning systems, online forums, sentiment analysis.

8. Conclusion

The study is conducted evaluating both performance-and-citation-related metrics and visualization techniques. The findings of this study present some valuable data related to prolific institutions, authors, sources, countries and trending keywords which are very important data in the emerging field of webometrics. This study also leaves ample scope to conduct a more extensive bibliometric investigation of global publications using more efficient network visualization tools as well as science mapping techniques to understand the collaboration behaviour, social and intellectual structure of the publications in the future.

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Global Trend of Research Publications on Coronavirus during 2016-2020 : a critical and comparative analysis among top ten countries

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Abstract

Human civilization witnessed different strain of coronavirus out of which last three - SARS-CoV (Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus), MARS-CoV (Middle East Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus) and SARS-CoV-2 (COVID-19) found highly pathogenic and caused fatal impact on humankind in the 21st century, especially COVID-19 emerged at the end of 2019 proved extremely dreadful which created global pandemic and still circulating in multiple variants in spite of continuous study and research worldwide to control the outbreak with protective measures, medicines and vaccines. Researches on coronavirus continued for decades by the scientists and researchers worldwide which suddenly boosted up with the advent of COVID-19. The study attempts to provide a critical and comparative analysis of research publications on the topic "coronavirus" among top ten countries of the world during 2016-20 as indexed in Web of Science (WOS) and retrieved on 27th July, 2021 with country-wise publication trend in the global race, citation, h-index, prolific authors, authorship pattern, degree of collaboration and most preferred journals.

Keywords : Authorship Pattern, Citation, CGAR, Coronavirus, Degree of Collaboration, H-index, Research publications

1. Introduction

The emergence of SARS Coronavirus (Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome) was noticed in Foshan, China in November 2002. The infection among individuals spread to Hong Kong, Vietnam, Canada and rapidly to several other countries in 2003. After 10 years from the first emergence SARS-CoV, a case found in Jordan in April, 2012 diagnosed as MARS-CoV (Middle East Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus). The coronavirus with new characteristics sporadically spread in Arabian Peninsula and South Korea as well, till 2016. In the existing threat of

Coronavirus, a new strain SARS-CoV-2 emerged in Wuhan, China in December, 2019 (COVID-19) and swiftly spread across the world significantly increased morbidity and mortality rate. Scientists, specialists and researchers from all corners of the world were involved in research on coronavirus for decades and the advent of COVID-19 suddenly intensified research challenges. The study attempts to provide a critical and comparative analysis of research publications on the topic "coronavirus" among top 10 countries of the world during 2016-20 as indexed in Web of Science (WOS) and

retrieved on 27th July, 2021 with country-wise publication trend in the global race, citation, h-index, prolific authors, authorship pattern, degree of collaboration and most preferred journals.

2. Literature review

Studies on Coronavirus initiated long back which became very proactive from the end of 2019 with the advent of COVID-19. The novel strain of coronavirus suddenly triggered the avalanche of research publication (Chahrour et. al, 2020) with reference to highly cited articles published during the span of 50 years since 1970 (Ram and Nisha, 2020). Attempts were made to gauge the global scientific output on the new threat of coronavirus (COVID-19) during early stage of the outbreak (Zyoud and Al-Jabi, 2020) using well established bibliometric indices and in the subsequent periods (Shiva Kumara, Sampat Kumar and Vinay, 2021). Research trend during last seven decades (1950-20) at the global level addressing coronavirus disclosed competitive productivity of USA and China than other countries (Mukherjee, 2020). The bibliometric landscape of Indian publications on COVID-19 in the year 2000 was exposed (Ghosh, 2021).

3. Objectives

- To measure the publication status of top ten countries in the trend of global publications on the topic "Coronavirus" during the years 2016-2020
- To examine the citation profile of top ten countries and gauge the citation impact in terms of h-index covering the period of study
- To review the prolific authors,

authorship pattern, degree of collaboration, most preferred journals.

4. Research limitations/implications

Research on the disease Coronavirus started long ago which became more extensive with the advent of novel Coronavirus named as COVID-19 at the end of 2019 and geared up subsequently resulted exponential growth of publication on coronavirus across the world. The study is limited to the publication of articles on coronavirus by the top ten countries of the world during 2016-2020.

5. Methodology

The data on the topic "Coronavirus" extracted from Web of Science database during 2016- 2020 on 27th July, 2021 for interpretation using search -

Topic : Coronavirus

Document Types: Articles

Publication Years: 2016 or 2017 or 2018 or 2019 or 2020

Countries/Regions: USA or PEOPLE'S REPUBLIC of CHINA or ITALY or ENGLAND or GERMANY or INDIA or CANADA or SPAIN or FRANCE or AUSTRALIA Subsequently, MS-Excel has been used for the analysis of data.

6. Data analysis and interpretation

6.1 Publication details

According to the data retrieved from the Web of Science (WOS), 21,141 articles published on the topic "Coronavirus" during 2016-2020 in the world and table 1 disclosed the year-wise feedback of top 10 countries with plotting in figure 1 and 2.

Table 1 : Year-wise distribution of publications by top ten counties during 2016-2020

Years	World	USA	China	Italy	England	Germany	India	Canada	Spain	France	Australia
2016	566	200	150	18	25	29	5	18	6	37	19
2017	578	190	157	21	37	44	10	29	11	20	19
2018	546	174	143	15	31	40	8	22	16	22	16
2019	592	183	166	15	35	36	15	27	15	30	15
2020	18,859	5,716	4,236	1,815	1,528	937	957	796	833	750	712
Total	21,141	6,463	4,852	1,884	1,656	1,086	995	892	881	859	781
% of World Pub.		30.57 %	22.95 %	8.91%	7.83%	5.13%	4.70 %	4.21%	4.16%	4.06%	3.69%
Ranking		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

Figure 1 : Total publications by top ten countries during 2016-2020

Figure 2 : Year-wise distribution of publications by top ten counties during 2016-2020

6.2 Growth rate of publications

The Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of the research productivity derived from the year-wise growth in the publication of research articles on coronavirus by top ten countries as mentioned in table 2 that determines the annual growth rate of the each country for a specific span of time.

$$CACR(t_0, t_n) = \left(\frac{V(t_n)}{V(t_0)} \right)^{\frac{1}{t_n - t_0}} - 1$$

where, $V(t_0)$: start value,

$V(t_n)$: finish value,

$t_n - t_0$: number of years.

Table 2 : CAGR ranking of top ten countries during 2016-2020

Top Ten Countries	Years										Total	CAGR	CAGR Rank
	2016		2017		2018		2019		2020				
	Pub	% *	Pub	% *	Pub	% *	Pub	% *	Pub	% *			
USA	200	3.095	190	2.940	174	2.692	183	2.832	5,716	88.442	6,463	95.53%	8
China	150	3.092	157	3.236	143	2.947	166	3.421	4,236	87.304	4,852	95.06%	9
Italy	18	0.955	21	1.115	15	0.796	15	0.796	1,815	96.338	1,884	151.61%	3
England	25	1.510	37	2.234	31	1.872	35	2.114	1,528	92.271	1,656	127.63%	4
Germany	29	2.670	44	4.052	40	3.683	36	3.315	937	86.280	1,086	100.39%	7
India	5	0.503	10	1.005	8	0.804	15	1.508	957	96.181	995	186.01%	1
Canada	18	2.018	29	3.251	22	2.466	27	3.027	796	89.238	892	113.37%	5
Spain	6	0.681	11	1.249	16	1.816	15	1.703	833	94.552	881	168.22%	2
France	37	4.307	20	2.328	22	2.561	30	3.492	750	87.311	859	82.55%	10
Australia	19	2.433	19	2.433	16	2.049	15	1.921	712	91.165	781	106.42%	6
	507		538		487		537		18,280		20,349		

* % of total publications of each country during 2016-2020

6.3 Citation profile of top 10 countries

The citation based measurements of top ten countries of the world in the publication of articles on Coronavirus during 2016-2020 has

been presented country-wise in the following table 3 and figure 3 as well as figure 4. The h-index has been regarded as the optimum measurement to evaluate the impact of scientific research.

Table 3 : Citation profile of top 10 countries during 2016-2020

Top Ten Countries	TP	TC	CA	ACPA	h-index	h-index Rank
USA	6463	224292	81970	34.70	203	2
China	4852	313251	85969	64.56	236	1
Italy	1884	55690	35252	29.56	103	4
England	1656	72778	44292	43.95	116	3
Germany	1086	54177	33231	49.89	95	5
India	995	14112	10231	14.18	56	10
Canada	892	31736	24582	35.58	77	7
Spain	881	26148	19304	29.68	66	9
France	859	36602	24921	42.61	81	6
Australia	781	30518	23489	39.08	71	8

TP : Total Publication of Articles; TC : Total Citations; CA : Citing Articles; ACP Average Citation Per Article

Figure 3 : Citation profile of top 10 countries on Coronavirus

Figure 4 : Ranking of top 10 countries during 2016-2020 as per h-index values

6.4 Prolific authors

As per publication counts on Coronavirus during 2016-2020 from top ten countries of the world, the authors from China

have published maximum number of articles than the prolific authors of other countries shown in table 4 as per the rank based on publication counts and drawn in figure 5.

Table 4: Prolific authors (top five) of top ten countries as per publication counts on Coronavirus

USA TP : 6463			China TP : 4852			Italy TP : 1884			England TP : 1656			Germany TP : 1086			India TP : 995			Canada TP:892			Spain TP:881			France TP:859			Australia TP:781		
Authors	Articles	% of T.P.	Authors	Articles	% of T.P.	Authors	Articles	% of T.P.	Authors	Articles	% of T.P.	Authors	Articles	% of T.P.	Authors	Articles	% of T.P.	Authors	Articles	% of T.P.	Authors	Articles	% of T.P.	Authors	Articles	% of T.P.			
Baric R S	75	1.160%	Wang Y	176	3.627%	Lippi G	23	1.221%	Zumla A	20	1.208%	Drosten C	58	5.341%	Kumar S	32	3.216%	Arabi Y M	19	2.130%	Segales J	15	1.703%	Raoult D	21	2.445%	Holmes E C	26	3.329%
Pertman S	54	0.836%	Zhang Y	147	3.030%	Ippolito G	18	0.955%	Zambon M	16	0.966%	Corman V M	34	3.131%	Kumar A	28	2.814%	Balkhy H H	14	1.570%	Enjuanes L	14	1.589%	Gautret P	14	1.630%	Macintyre C R	13	1.665%
Li Y	39	0.603%	Wang J	137	2.824%	Ciccozzi M	17	0.902%	Hayden F G	15	0.906%	Muller M A	27	2.486%	Kumar V	23	2.312%	Hayden F G	13	1.457%	Bensaid A	11	1.249%	Tortorici M A	14	1.630%	Cheng A C	11	1.408%
Wang Y	39	0.603%	Li Y	129	2.659%	Bruno R	15	0.796%	Bickerton E	13	0.785%	Hartmann K	18	1.657%	Singh S	23	2.312%	Fowler R A	12	1.345%	Sola I	11	1.249%	Colson P	13	1.513%	Bhaskar S	10	1.280%
Zhang Y	37	0.572%	Liu Y	127	2.617%	Galli M	15	0.796%	Britton P	13	0.785%	Ziebuhr J	17	1.565%	Kumar R	20	2.010%	Mubareka S	12	1.345%	Fernandezruiz M	10	1.135%	La Scola B	13	1.513%	Li J	10	1.280%

Figure 5 : Prolific authors (top five) of top ten countries as per publication counts on Coronavirus

6.5 Authorship pattern

The study on authorship pattern reflects the involvement of the number of authors in research publication on a particular topic.

Table 5 and figure 6 projected the authorship pattern of publications on Coronavirus of top ten countries of the world during the years 2016-2020 with ranking.

Table 5 : Authorship pattern of top ten countries on Coronavirus during 2016-2020

Authorship	USA	China	Italy	England	Germany	India	Canada	Spain	France	Australia	Total	Rank
1	341	60	33	95	36	44	44	30	21	46	750	11
2	526	135	85	130	57	139	59	51	38	64	1284	8
3	654	237	113	139	73	133	75	65	44	59	1592	5
4	596	352	140	127	79	143	70	75	56	74	1712	2
5	585	389	144	136	72	107	79	55	56	73	1696	3
6	514	421	159	115	78	101	82	88	57	52	1667	4
7	456	461	150	111	76	74	58	62	48	56	1552	6
8	399	464	124	83	67	60	49	51	66	41	1404	7
9	325	364	113	74	62	37	31	48	43	29	1126	9
10	306	352	114	56	64	28	31	41	42	39	1073	10
>10	1761	1617	709	590	422	129	314	315	388	248	6493	1
	6463	4852	1884	1656	1086	995	892	881	859	781	20349	

Figure 6 : Authorship pattern of top ten countries on Coronavirus during 2016-2020

6.6 Degree of collaboration

Collaboration in research can be considered very essential to increase the growth of publication. The authorship collaboration of top ten countries in the publication of articles on Coronavirus during 2016-2020 measured with the following formula suggested by Subramanyam (1982) :

$$DC = N_M / N_M + N_S$$

where

DC = Degree of Collaboration

NS = Number of Single Authors

NM = Number of Multiple Authors

Figure 7: Degree of collaboration of top ten countries in article publication on Coronavirus during 2016-20

Table 6 has revealed the number of collaborative publications to the total number of publications on Coronavirus individually as well as in total by top ten countries of the world during 2016-20 with display in figure 7 with the degree of collaboration found 0.96.

Table 6: Degree of collaboration of top ten countries in article publication on Coronavirus during 2016-20

Top Ten Countries	Articles of Single Author (N _S)	Articles of Multiple Authors (N _M)	Total (N _S + N _M)	Degree of Collaboration(DC)
USA	341	6122	6463	0.95
China	60	4792	4852	0.99
Italy	33	1851	1884	0.98
England	95	1561	1656	0.94
Germany	36	1050	1086	0.97
India	44	951	995	0.95
Canada	44	848	892	0.95
Spain	30	851	881	0.96
France	21	838	859	0.97
Australia	46	735	781	0.94
Total	750	19599	20349	0.96

6.7 Preferred journals of top 10 countries in publication of articles on Coronavirus (2016-20)

The top 5 preferred journals of top 10

countries of the world on the publication of articles on Coronavirus during the years 2016-2020 listed in table 7 and displayed in figure 8.

Figure 8: Preferred top 5 journals of top 10 countries - publication of articles on "Coronavirus" (2016-20)

7. Research findings

- 1) As per year-wise publication counts retrieved from WoS during 2016-2020, massive surge of publication of articles on the topic "Coronavirus" at the global level is noticed in the year 2020 than the previous years. Out of total 21141 articles published during 5 years, 18859 articles have been published in 2020.
- 2) Top 10 countries have published 20349 articles out of 21141 articles published globally on the topic of "Coronavirus" during 2016-2020 (5 years). USA has achieved 1st rank for publishing maximum number of articles (6463 articles) on the said topic followed by China ranked 2nd publishing 4852 articles. Italy occupies 3rd rank with 1884 articles.
- 3) Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of research productivity in the publication of articles on "Coronavirus" during 2016-2020 has reflected that India ranked 1st (186.1%) followed by Spain (rank-2nd - 168.225), Italy (rank 3 - 151.61%).
- 4) The citation profile of top 10 countries in respect to the publication of articles on "Coronavirus" during 2016-2020 has disclosed the highest h-index value in favour of China (236). USA and England with h-index value of 203 and 116 have ranked 2nd and 3rd position respectively.
- 5) Among top 5 prolific authors of top 10 countries in the publication of articles on "Coronavirus" during 2016-2020, all the 5 authors from China have published maximum number of articles than the authors of other countries considered in the study. Wang Y of China has published 176 articles, 3.627% of total publications of China has achieved 1st rank followed by Zhang Y (147 articles - 3.030% T.P. of China) with 2nd rank and Wang J (147 articles - 3.030% T.P. of China) with third rank.
- 6) The authorship pattern on "Coronavirus" during 2016-2020 has indicated that out of 20349 articles by top 10 countries at the global level, the single authorship contribution has been counted only 750 (3.69%) and rest 19599 (96.31%) articles has been found multi-authored publications.

Considering the number of collaborative publications to the total number of publications, the degree of collaboration is found 0.96.

- 7) The top 5 preferred journals to publish the articles on "Coronavirus" by the top 10 countries at the global level during the years 2016-2020 have been listed with the publication counts, where China holds highest position publishing 146 articles in the "Journal of Medical Virology" followed by India and USA with 127 articles in the "Journal of Biomolecular Structure Dynamics" and 114 articles in "Plos One" respectively.

8. Conclusion

The threatening of "Coronavirus" pandemic with different variants still continuing at the global level has resulted growth of publications on rapid progression on research, case study, test early investigation protocol, clinical care and management, considerations for treatment of infected patients from asymptomatic to critically ill. Further research on changing variants of Coronavirus, track the spread and virulence of the virus, vaccination, medicine, other relevant measures to protect health and prevent the spread of the outbreak have brought exponential growth in research publications globally since 2020.

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The Information Practices of Fishermen Community in Canning Subdivision of South 24 Parganas District: a case study

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Abstract

This paper attempts to evaluate the information practices of fishermen community in Canning subdivision of South 24 Parganas district. The main purpose of this study is to identify the basic information needs of the fishermen and find out the appropriate sources of information. Mainly the survey method was used for data collection. In this study, 150 fishermen in total were randomly selected from the four blocks (Basanti, Canning I, Canning II and Gosaba) of Canning subdivision. Data were collected from sampling persons by questionnaire with the help of personal interview conducted by the researcher. The findings of this study reveal about the sex, age group, religion, marital status, type of family, level of education and monthly income of the fishermen community in this region. This study also investigates the various types of information needs such as technical, climatic, environmental, economic and so on. Also the different type of information sources used by the fishermen has also been described here. This study is an original depiction of the information practices of fishermen community of Canning subdivision.

Keywords : Canning subdivision, Fishermen community, Fishing, Information needs, Information practices, Information source

1. Introduction

In most of the developed and developing countries, fishing is an important sector from the viewpoint of income and employment. Fishing industry also supports some income generator professions such as processing of fishing boats, refrigeration and ice making, gear and equipment manufacturers and transport services. It also provides protein-rich food, several items for sell like fish meal, fish oil, fish scales, fish manure etc. There are two types of fisheries such as marine fisheries and inland fisheries which can be categorized

as capture and culture fisheries.

In spite of the development of the fisheries sectors, the fishermen community lives in a low status in society. Various elements like low economic status, poor social conditions, illiteracy, use of traditional fishing equipments and methods of fishing low production rate and income affect the socio-economic conditions of fishermen. Therefore, socio-economic progress of fishermen is important for proper development of the fishing industry in India.

2. Area profile

It is obvious that the present study deals with the information practices of fishermen community in the Canning subdivision. There are four blocks named Basanti, Canning 1, Canning 2 and Gosaba. The survey of this study is confined to these particular 4 blocks of this district. The scope of the study is limited only to fishermen of these blocks.

The District Human Development Report, South 24 Parganas, writes, "Canning has emerged as a major market for supply of fish to Kolkata. The fishermen of the area bring their catch to the all-night fish market at Canning. Here the commission agents receive the fish and auction them. It is bought by the wholesalers and transported to Kolkata for sale to retailers, who sell it in different markets".

3. Review of literature

It is implied that everyone can create, access, share and utilize information in the information society to acquire their information need (Hossain, 2012) and also information seeking process of a professional begins with a subjective task (Zoontjes, 2015) that leads to information need is influenced by different factors (Kundu, 2017). It has been showed that the research scholars seek for information for writing research articles (Singh & Khanchandani, 2015) whereas the post-graduate students seek information for their study (Ajiboye, 2007) are mostly collected from the internet by utilization of data in the term of session and pages viewed were more than the other academic community (David, 2009). Students and faculties of professional course like Dentistry always prefer to access specialized information which fulfills the special need in their professional field (Biswas, Chakrabarti, & Das Biswas, 2013). It has also been identified that information seeking behaviour

of rural inhabitants of one region varies from the other region on the basis of socio-economic condition (Shariful Islam & Ahmed, 2012) whereas the farmer's information seeking behaviours are gender specific (Lwoga, Ngulube & Stilwell, 2010). It indicates to the poor information skills (Ali Amour, 2017), suffering for poverty (Bakar, 2011), remote location of the libraries (Shukla, 2018), language barrier, internet connection, computing, use of database are some barriers during the time of information seeking (Mussa & António, 2020). The information needs of fishermen are mostly occupation directed and their chief sources of information include colleagues, friends, neighbours, relatives (Njoku, 2004), fellow farmers, the technicians of the feed (Alagappan & Kumaran, 2020). Use of mobile phone plays an important role (Ifejika, 2016) and with the help of mobile technology and information technology (Mandalia & Joshi, 2020) majority of fishermen fulfill their information need related day-to-day activities (Ramadas & Saravanan, 2016). It has also been revealed that fisher folk require different kinds of information to carry out fishing activities effectively (Ikoja-Odongo & Ocholla, 2003) related to loan facility, fish processing, preservation, modern fishing equipment (Otolu, 2009) and also for health, climate, type of vessels, type of fish net, fishing, education needs of their children, marketing information (Vanaja, 2015), fish price, fishing instruments, weather and so on (Rachman, 2019). Fishermen faces problems to acquire information in marine fishing (Saha, 2006) that led to belong half of the fishermen to low level (Oli et.al 2019).

It is very essential to understand information seeking behaviour to satisfy the information need by providing the available sources. The fishermen community is one of the important parts of our society. The studies

so far have been conducted on fishermen bring forth their various information need and level of satisfaction in terms of availability of required information.

4. Statement of the problem

The studied literatures have focused on fishermen community of various regions within India and outside India. But no such literature is found which highlighted the information practices of fishermen community in West Bengal. As already mentioned in the area profile about the importance of fish market in Canning subdivision where lot of fishermen are connected to supply the fishes. Those who are playing such an important role to supply the favourite food of Bengalis in Kolkata and its suburban areas have not been studied so far properly in terms of their information practices. Therefore this study comes forward to fill up this research gap and has been entitled as "The Information Practices of Fishermen Community in Canning Subdivision of South 24 Parganas District: a case study".

5. Objectives

The objectives of the study have been set forth as:

1. To identify the information needs of fishermen community

2. To determine the sources of information used by the fishermen community

3. To study the social conditions and social status of fishermen

6. Methodology

To conduct the study mainly the survey method was used for data collection. A stratified accidental random sample method was used for the selection of respondents those who were found during the survey period, viz., May to October, 2021. Based on the simple random sampling procedure, 150 fishermen were randomly selected for study from the four blocks (Basanti, Canning I, Canning II and Gosaba) of Canning subdivision. Data were collected from sampling persons by questionnaire with the help of personal interviews conducted by the researcher. The collected data has been presented in the form of a table and then analyzed. For representation of data, some graphical methods such as bars, pie charts are used for perception of data more clearly, effectively and constructively.

7. Findings and discussion

With the stated methodology data has been collected to fulfill the stated objectives of this study. The collected data has been presented in the following way with appropriate interpretation:

7.1 General information about the fishermen

Table 1: General information about the fishermen in the Canning subdivision

General Information		Respondents (n=150)	
		No	%
Sex	Male	87	58
	Female	63	42
Age Group	Below 20 year	5	3.33
	20 to 30 years	13	8.67
	30 to 40 years	36	24
	40 to 50 years	49	32.67
	above 50 years	45	30
Religion	Hindu	76	50.67
	Muslim	66	44
	Christian	2	1.33
	Others	6	4
Marital status	Married	134	89.33
	Unmarried	16	10.67
Type of family	Nuclear family	101	67.33
	Extended family	26	17.33
	Joint family	23	15.33
Level of education	Up to primary school	28	18.67
	Up to High school	87	58
	Up to Higher Secondary	13	8.67
	Up to Graduate course	4	2.67
	Illiterate	18	12
Monthly income	Below Rs. 5000	31	20.67
	Between 5001 to 10000	76	50.67
	Between 10001 to 15000	22	14.67
	Between 15001 to 20000	13	8.67
	Above 20000	8	5.33

Data of table 1 has been shown general information about the respondents. This data also exposes about sex, age group, religion, marital status, type of family, level of education and monthly income of the respondents. Most of the fishermen are male 87(58%) among the respondents. Most of the respondents belong in age between 40 to 50 years 49(32.67%) rather than other age group above 50 years 45(30%), 30 to 40 years

36(24%), 20 to 30 years 13(8.67%) and below 20 year 5(3.33%). Observing the data about the religion of fishermen, it has been shown that there are Hindu 76(50.67%) followed by the Muslim 66(44%), Christian 2(1.33%) and others 6(4%) among the respondents. Most of the respondents are married 134(89.33%) rather than unmarried 16(10.67%). The family in this area is nuclear family 101(67.33%), extended family 26(17.33%)

and joint family 23(15.33%). Education level of most of the respondents are up to high school 87(58%), up to primary school 28(18.67%), up to higher secondary 13(8.67%), up to graduate course 4(2.67%) and illiterate are 18(12%). According to the survey results, 76(50.67%) respondents earn

between Rs.5001 and 10,000 a month, 31 (20.67%) have income below Rs.5,000, 22(14.67%) have income between Rs.10001 and 15000, 13(14.67%) have income between Rs.15001 and 200000, and 8 (5.33%) have income above Rs.20000.

7.2 Information needs of fishermen

Table 2: Distribution of basic information needs of fishermen community

Sl. No.	Type of information	Always		Sometimes		Never	
		No	%	No	%	No	%
a)	Technical information	67	44.67	44	29.33	39	26
b)	Climate	96	57.33	37	24.67	17	11.33
c)	Environmental Information	54	36	62	41.33	34	22.67
d)	Current Information	84	56	37	24.67	29	19.33
e)	Economic Information	87	58	48	32	15	10
f)	Socio-Cultural Information	58	38.67	53	35.33	39	26
g)	Geographical Information	69	46	44	29.33	37	24.67
h)	Health Information	78	52	47	31.33	25	16.67

By analyzing the data from table 2, we can understand about the information needs of the fishermen community of the mentioned sample area. Most of the fishermen of that region always need information about climate 96(64%) followed by the economic information 87(58%), current information 84(56%), health information 78(52%),

geographic information 69(46%), technological information 67(44.67%), socio-cultural information 58(38.67%) and environmental information 54(36%). It is obvious from the table 2 that the fishermen of Canning subdivision also need various type of information for betterment of their profession

7.3 Major Information Sources

Table 3: Sources of information used by fisherman

Information Sources		Regularly		Sometimes		Never	
		No	%	No	%	No	%
Conventional Sources	Library-Public library	41	27.33	72	48	37	24.67
	Books	21	14	67	44.67	62	41.33
	Journal and magazine	56	37.33	59	39.33	35	23.33
	Community centers	46	30.67	66	44	38	25.33
	Fishing department	34	22.67	63	42	53	35.33
	Fisheries university	27	18	37	24.67	86	57.33
	Government Organization	38	25.33	43	28.66	69	46
Non-conventional Sources	Information through internet	27	18	54	36	69	46
	Social media	87	58	38	25.33	25	16.67
	Radio	121	80.67	19	12.67	10	6.67
	Mobile phone	76	50.67	41	27.33	33	22
	GPS	64	42.67	34	22.67	52	34.67
	Poster	22	14.67	54	36	74	49.33
	Television	105	70	18	12	27	18
Indigenous Sources	Friends/Relative	115	76.67	21	14	14	9.33
	Market place	127	84.67	18	12	5	3.33
	Community leaders	36	24	65	43.33	49	32.67
	Co-workers	111	74	25	16.67	14	9.33

Table 3 shows that there are three kinds of information sources such as conventional sources, non-conventional sources and indigenous sources used by the fishermen community and their frequencies of use also

categorized into 3 types as regularly, sometimes and never. The data represents the number of respondents who use the particular information sources.

Figure 1: Major information sources

From figure number 1, it has been shown that non-conventional sources and indigenous sources are more used rather than conventional sources. Among the indigenous sources, most of the respondents collect information from market place 127(84.67%) followed by friend/ relative 115(76.67%), co-workers 111(74%) and community leaders 46(30.67%), library 41(27.33%), government organization 38(25.33%), fishing department 34(22.67%), fisheries university 27(18%), books 21(14%).

phone 76(50.67%), GPS 64(42.67%) and poster 22(14.67%). All conventional sources are also essential for fulfill the information need of fishermen. Among those sources, most of the fishermen collect information regularly from journal and magazine 56(37.33%) rather than community centers 46(30.67%), library 41(27.33%), government organization 38(25.33%), fishing department 34(22.67%), fisheries university 27(18%), books 21(14%).

7.4 Ownership of assets

Table 4: Ownership of assets acquired by the fishermen

Assets		No. of respondents (n=150)	
		No	%
Mobile phone	Yes	127	84.67
	No	23	15.33
Electricity	General electricity	88	58.67
	Solar electricity	43	28.67
	No electricity	19	12.67
Television	Yes	93	62
	No	57	38
Radio	Yes	113	75.33
	No	37	24.67

Analyzed data from table 4 enlighten about the assets of fishermen in this region. A large number of fishermen have mobile phones (84.67%), radios (75.33%), televisions (93%) and electricity (88%).

7.5 Use of social media

Table 5: Used of social media by the fishermen community

Social media	Below 20 y		20 to 30 y		30 to 40 y		40 to 50 y		Above 50 y		Total	%
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%		
Facebook	4	2.67	11	7.33	27	18	14	9.33	16	10.67	72	48
WhatsApp	4	2.67	9	6	27	18	17	11.33	14	9.33	71	47.33
YouTube	5	3.33	9	6	29	19.33	22	14.67	21	14	86	57.33
Twitter	0		1	0.67	0		0		0		1	0.66
Others	0		0		0		0		0		0	0

Table 5 represents the uses of different types of social media like Facebook, WhatsApp, YouTube, Twitter by fishermen from different age group.

Figure 2: Use of social media

Use of social media by the fishermen is known from the figure 2. Most of the fishermen fulfill their information need by using the social media like YouTube 86(57.33%) followed by the Face book 72(48%), WhatsApp 71(47.33%) and Twitter 1(0.66%).

8. Conclusion and suggestions

A certain conclusion can be drawn from the study of information practices of fishermen community in Canning subdivision. From the above explanation, it is obvious that the fishermen community have the need of various type of information such as technical information, current information, economic information, geographical information, information about climate and information about health more frequently for improvement their fishing techniques, utilization of modern implements and equipment. Most of the fisherman use friends/relative, market place, co-workers as their major source to satisfy their information need. They also use mobile phones, television and radio to understand their occupation better. It also shows that the social media like Facebook, WhatsApp, YouTube, Twitter etc.

are more used by age groups below 20 years to 40 years old rather than 40 years to above 50 years old.

Some suggestions have been made in the following:

- The government should increase sufficient library services to expand the use of conventional sources more.
- Adult education programmes should be organized to increase their information utilization capacity.
- An attempt should have been made to disseminate the right information to the friends, relatives, family members, co-workers as they are the major information sources to the fishermen.
- The fishermen should be encouraged to use electronic gadgets more to satisfy their information need.

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Trend of Coronavirus Disease Research during the Period from 2010 to 2019: a bibliometric study

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Abstract

Coronavirus disease has appeared as one of the most devastating global epidemics in the 21st century. The aim of the present study is to display the progress of research activities examined on the field during last decade. The work widely covered the trend of entire coronavirus disease research field of PubMed Central Database. The Database was used to collect the articles related to coronavirus disease published from 2010 to 2019. VOSviewer v. 1.6.15 and MS Excel were used for bibliometric analysis. Total 3539 documents were collected, in which United States of America and China contributed maximum papers and National Institute of Health, USA was the highest contributor. Among journals, the 'Viruses' contributed the most and maximum number of articles were written in 2019. International collaboration is the only solution to strengthen research progress and gain success. Development of suitable vaccines and drugs are the further research directions.

Keywords : Bibliometric analysis, Coronavirus Disease, Global epidemics, Middle East Respiratory Syndrome, PubMed Central Database, Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome.

1. Introduction

Coronavirus infection attacked repeatedly in various parts of the world and unfortunately brought three widespread epidemics. In December 2019, pneumonia with unknown symptoms and causes happened in the provinces Wuhan, Hubei of China (Lou et al., 2020). SARS-CoV-2 is recently introduced as coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) by the World Health Organization. The virus infecting human body is the seventh human coronavirus (Peiris et al., 2003).

There is need to establish an estimation of knowledge, awareness and practice among people towards the coronavirus disease

infections along with a consciousness and educational programme with updated experimental research information. Bibliometric study is a commonly accepted statistical tool and it helps to present knowledge structures of a particular research domain. Throughout recent years, bibliometrics have been used to provide sound perception into several biomedical fields which are related to many virus outbreaks. The purpose of the present study is to explore the distribution of research capabilities of countries, institutions and the researchers, and also the problematic areas and probable solutions of coronavirus disease research field in the last ten years (Sturenburg & Hufert, 2018). The study is important

because,

- It will provide the researchers a foresight about the future thrust areas of coronavirus disease field and
- It will provide suggestions so that librarian can do the necessary action in support of coronavirus disease scholarship and research.

2. Literature review

Chahrour (2020) conducted a study to explore the activity and trends of COVID-19 research since its emergence in December and gained conclusion that COVID-19 is a major disease that impacted international public health on a global level. Observational studies and therapeutic trials pertaining to COVID-19 are essential for assessing pathogenic characteristics and developing novel treatment options.

Farooq and others (2021) examined the literature of coronavirus disease (COVID19), which were published in the database Web of Science through the year 2019-20 with the help of bibliometric methods.

Haghani and others (2020) analyzed the bibliometric aspects of publications published in various databases. A holistic interdisciplinary approach and a collective scientific effort are required to help understand the various safety impact of this problem.

Kambhupati, Vaishya and Vaish (2020) carried out a bibliometric analytical study and showed an unexpected growth of publications on COVID-19 since the disease started. The rate of publications of nearly 59 articles per day is probably the highest for any disease published so far.

Shri Ram (2020) traced the trends of research associated with "Coronavirus" for a period of 50 years using the SCOPUS

database. The study was carried out using the keyword and analyzed for annual growth, productive countries, institutes, authors, journals, highly cited papers and research focus using keywords.

Verma and Gustafsson (2020) tried to find out the emerging COVID-19 research trends in the business and management field. The findings identified the most active authors and sub-areas of research on business context related to COVID-19. The work also gave existing subjective and evaluative literature reviews on present research.

Yang (2020) focused on traditional Chinese medicine research for coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) and concluded that the research activities were scattered and the cooperation between authors and academic institutions, universities and funding agencies needed to be further strengthened. Integrative research system will upgrade the quality of research output.

Zhai and others (2020) made a bibliometric analysis of global research progress on Coronavirus during 2003 to 2020 based on Web of Science database clarified that 11,036 articles were written and USA and China contributed maximum papers on the literature.

Zhou and Chen (2020) worked on global coronavirus research trends during 2000 to 2020 17th March on Web of Science core collection database. Among contributing countries, China was standing in first position and Journal of Virology submitted most of the articles. The study revealed the urgent need of collaborative research work and doing more research in the field of prevention and treatment strategies.

Zyoud and Al-jabi (2020) mapped the situation of research on coronavirus disease-2019 (COVID-19), during the primary stage of the outbreak based on Scopus database

during December 2019 to 19th June 2020 and observed that out of 19,044 documents, only 9140 were articles and rest were letters, reviews, editorials and notes. Most prolific journal was British Medical Journal. The findings indicated new way on the major progress in the near future for unique topics on COVID-19 research including clinical features studies, pathological findings, therapeutic design, infection control etc.

3. Statement of the problem

Comparing earlier studies, it may be understood that during past time, research activity had been limited to the study of mainly six viral infectious diseases: Chikungunya, Dengue, Ebola, Lyme, West Nile and Zika. The present work may be considered as significant in this perspective. The end users of this study are mainly the researchers of Biomedical Science and librarian or information professionals. From this study it will be possible to achieve a scenario of expansion of literature in Coronavirus disease in living species, especially human being, throughout the world during the present global pandemic period. The previously published bibliometric studies on a single strain COVID-19 have been prepared by using Web of Science, Scopus or World Health Organization database for data collection. Here PubMed Central database was used for retrieving data. Therefore the intention of the current study is to assess the global scientific output of Coronavirus disease research during 2019 to 2019 through bibliometric analysis.

4. Objectives of the study

The objectives of the study are:

- to measure the annual growth of literature during the study period
- to study the distribution of research capabilities of countries, academic

institutions and journals of Coronavirus disease research in the past one decade

- to examine the authorship pattern and degree of collaboration (DC) of the articles
- to understand the core areas of research of the present literature
- to find out the use of important basic terms in the total literature and
- to analyze the distribution of language in the present literature.

5. Methodology

5.1 Scope and coverage

The present study has attempted to analyse the research output performance of global scientists in the field of Coronavirus disease was confined to the article/papers written on the topic coronavirus disease by researchers around the world, published in various journals of medical sciences. The journals were retrieved from PubMed Central database, NCBI only. The duration was taken from the year 2010 to 2019.

5.2 Methods used

The required data which were retrieved from PubMed Central Database, United States National Library of Medicine was also evaluated from NLM catalog record. The total search system was executed by Automatic Term Mapping System of Pubmed Central digital repository and search terms were: corona virus disease AND (("2010/01/01" [PDat]: "2019/12/31" [PDat])). Detailed keywords and Boolean operators were : (Corona [All Fields] AND ("virus diseases"[MeSH Terms] OR ("virus"[All Fields] AND "diseases"[All Fields]) OR "virus diseases"[All Fields] OR ("virus"[All Fields] AND "disease"[All Fields]) OR "virus disease" [All Fields])) AND

("2010/01/01"[PubDate] : "2019/12/31"[PubDate]) The terms were mapped by Medical Subject Heading terms and the time range was 01/01/2010 to 31/12/2019. Primarily retrieved 3650 documents from PubMed Central archive became finally 3539 Peer-reviewed articles after excluding 21 Proceedings, 47 Meeting-Abstracts and 43 Reviews. The PubMed records were first transferred into MEDLINE format and imported into an EndNote library and were

finally recorded in a Microsoft Excel Spreadsheet format. VOSviewer software, Leiden University (Version 1.6.15) was used for quantifying the frequency and density of coronavirus disease articles core terminologies.

6. Data analysis and results

The data obtained through the stated methodology have been presented in the following ways:

Table 1: Analysis of the trend of annual publications

Sl. No.	Year	Total Publication	Percentage (%)	Cumulative Total	Cumulative Percentage (%)
1	2010	234	6.612	234	6.612
2	2011	185	5.23	419	11.84
3	2012	250	7.06	669	18.9
4	2013	301	8.5	970	27.4
5	2014	367	10.4	1337	37.8
6	2015	332	9.4	1669	47.2
7	2016	303	8.56	1972	55.72
8	2017	486	13.8	2458	69.45
9	2018	449	12.7	2907	82.14
10	2019	632	17.85	3539	100
		3539	100 %		

Table 1 clearly shows the annual growth of publications. There was an up down trend from 2010 to 2019. Among 3539 articles, the highest number of papers was written on the year 2019(632; 17.85%). In 2011, the lowest

185(5.23%) papers were published by PubMed Central database. But the growth was increased during 2012-2014, and 2018-2019 due to SARS-Cov and COVID-19 outbreak respectively.

Table 2: Analysis of Countries/Territories

Rank	Countries/Territories	Articles	Percentage (%)
1	USA	809	22.9
2	China	779	22
3	Italy	621	17.5
4	United Kingdom	425	12
5	Canada	209	6
6	Germany	197	5.56
7	Australia	89	2.6
8	Korea	87	2.4
9	The Netherlands	72	2.03
10	France	69	1.9
11	Spain	57	1.6
12	Finland	43	1.2
13	Portugal	32	0.9
14	Norway	22	0.62
15	Congo	17	0.48

Table 2 clarifies that USA was dominating the field, followed by China, Italy and United Kingdom. China was the country where SARS and COVID-19 broke out and severely struck. European countries were dominating the research field. Only Latin

American country was Brazil. Fifteen countries presented in the table add the heterogeneous nature of the research work. Almost all countries had been engaged themselves (despite financial discrimination) in carrying out fruitful, relevant experiments.

Table 3: Analysis of research areas

Rank	Research Area	Total Documents	Percentage
1	Molecular Biology	858	24.3
2	Pharmacology	661	18.7
3	Virology	631	17.8
4	Microbiology	562	15.9
5	Infectious Diseases	446	12.6
6	Veterinary Sciences	191	5.4
7	Immunology	101	2.8
8	Neurosciences	89	2.5

Table 3 proves that the source journals containing coronavirus disease research were mainly distributed in eight fields - Molecular Biology, Pharmacology (Nanomedicine, Vaccine, Antibody Preparation), Virology, Microbiology, Infectious Diseases,

Veterinary Sciences, Immunology and Neurosciences. Molecular Biology (858; 24.3%), Pharmacology (661; 18.7%) and Virology (631; 17.8%) were the basis of coronavirus disease research.

Table 4: Analysis of language

Rank	Language	Contribution	Percentage (%)
1	English	3520	99.5
2	German	9	0.25
3	Spanish	5	0.14
4	Dutch	3	0.08
5	French	1	0.02
6	Portuguese	1	0.02

Table 4 reveals that, total 3539 articles were collected from the PubMed Central database. Among them, 99.5 % (3520) articles were written in English language; and the rest were published in German (9; 0.25%),

Spanish (5; 0.14%), Dutch (3; 0.08%), French (1; 0.02%) and Portuguese (1; 0.02%). It proves that English is still the base language of scientific research.

Table 5: Analysis of most contributing journals

Rank	Journal Name	No. of Documents	Percentage (%)	Impact Factor
1	Viruses	823	23.3 %	3.816
2	Archives of Virology	498	14.07 %	2.230
3	Journal of Virological Methods	282	8 %	1.786
4	Journal of Clinical Virology	178	5.02 %	2.777
5	The Open Virology Journal	171	4.83 %	0.25
6	Virus as Populations	167	4.71 %	3.816
7	Future Virology	159	4.5 %	0.500
8	Influenza And Other Respiratory Viruses	102	2.8 %	3.060
9	Cytokine	87	2.5 %	2.880
10	Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews-RNA	73	2.06 %	6.913
11	American Journal of Infection Control	61	1.8 %	2.030
12	Nanomedicine	58	1.7 %	4.140
13	Antiviral Research	52	1.5 %	4.120
14	Microbes And Infection	48	1.4 %	2.373
15	Research In Veterinary Science	37	1.04 %	0.637

[Impact Factor based on Clarivate Analytics 'Journal Citation Reports 2019'; which was published in 2020]

From table 5 it is clarified that retrieved articles were published in different prominent

journals. Among them, the journal 'Viruses' ranked first (823; 23.3 %), followed by 'Archives of Virology' (498; 14.07%), and 'Journal of Virological Methods' (282; 8%). There was a long gap between first and second position. The result is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Analysis of most contributing journals

Table 6: Analysis of the most productive institutions

Rank	Institutions/University	Countries/Territories	Articles	Percentage (%)
1	National Institutes of Health	USA	435	12.3
2	California State University	USA	328	9.26
3	Sichuan University	Sichuan,China	248	7
4	King Saud University	Saudi Arabia	242	6.9
5	University de Montreal	Canada	214	6.04
6	Chinese Academy of Sciences	China	210	5.93
7	University of Helsinki	Finland	203	5.73
8	Auburn University	USA	178	5.02
9	Nippon Veterinary and Life Science University	Japan	173	4.89
10	University of Washington	Seattle, USA	165	4.66
11	John Innes Centre, Norwich	United Kingdom	163	4.6
12	Utrecht University	The Netherlands	157	4.43
13	World Health Organization	Geneva, Switzerland	141	3.98
14	University of Freiburg	Germany	140	3.95
15	University of Naples	Italy	138	3.89

The contributions of the 15 most productive institutions have been analyzed in the table 6. National Institutes of Health, which published 435 (12.3%) articles in the database, got first position followed by California State University (328; 9.26%);

Sichuan University West China Hospital, Sichuan (248; 7%). Among these, six were from USA, with two from China and the rest were other countries. The result proved USA's dominance in this particular research field.

Table 7: Analysis of the keywords

Rank	Keywords	Frequency of Use
1	Human Coronavirus-NL63	10,033
2	Middle East Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus	8882
3	Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus	8875
4	Coronaviridae	4233
5	Viral Replication	1629
6	Isolation	1249
7	N-Protein	1023
8	Genome Sequence	935
9	Epidemic	762
10	Phylogenetic	718
11	Bronchiolitis	564
12	Respiratory Tract	531
13	Immune System	403
14	Dromedary camels	319
15	Zoonotic	221

Table 7 analyses the frequency of use of prominent keywords in the entire text. The top three keywords with the highest frequency were - HCoV-NL63 (10,033); Middle East

Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus (8882) and Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus (8875).

Table 8: Authorship pattern of articles (year-wise)

Year	Single	Two	Three	Four	Five & Above	Total
2010	8	34	63	---	129	234
2011	----	----	16	68	101	185
2012	34	56	51	11	98	250
2013	27	41	----	203	30	301
2014	----	69	99	60	139	367
2015	50	---	99	64	119	332
2016	17	----	----	185	101	303
2017	20	----	----	267	199	486
2018	15	33	2	101	298	449
2019	9	82	----	175	366	632
	180	315	330	1134	1580	3539

Table 8 shows the authorship pattern of the articles. The five and above authored articles were highest in the database i.e., 1580 (44.7%), followed by four-authored articles (1134; 32.04 %); three-authored articles (330; 9.32 %). Single-authored articles were lowest in number (180; 5.08 %). This reveals a rising tendency towards collaborative research.

Table 9: Analysis of degree of collaboration (year-wise)

Year	Single-Authored Papers (Ns)	Multi-Authored Papers (Nm)	Degree of Collaboration (DC)
2010	8	226	0.96
2011	-	185	1
2012	34	216	0.86
2013	27	274	0.91
2014	-	367	1
2015	50	282	0.84
2016	17	286	0.94

Year	Single-Authored Papers (Ns)	Multi-Authored Papers (Nm)	Degree of Collaboration (DC)
2017	20	466	0.95
2018	15	434	0.89
2019	9	623	0.98
Total	180	3359	0.94 (Mean DC)

Table 9 indicates the tendency of single and joint authorship in the various scientific journals on Coronavirus disease research literature during 2010 to 2019. The average degree of collaboration was 0.94 during the

period under the study. It proves that there existed the highest collaboration among the authors in the literature of Coronavirus disease research. The fluctuation is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Analysis of degree of collaboration (year-wise)

6. Findings

The findings are prepared mainly on the basis of the objectives of the study. The major findings of the present study can be summarized as below:

- The study reveals that, a total of 3539 articles were published during 2010 to 2019. Among them, the highest number of articles was published in 2019 [vide table 1].
- Among contributing countries all over the world, United States of America is in the first position and China ranked second. The journal "Viruses" contributed the most in terms of research productivity. National Institutes of Health of USA is currently the most productive academic body which published most of the articles [vide tables 2, 5, 6].
- Authorship pattern displayed a wide range from single authorship to a collaborative group effort of as many as 18 authors. The present study identifies that 94.91% articles were produced under joint authorship and average degree of collaboration is 0.94. The collaborative status reached peak point in the year 2011 and 2014 [vide tables 8 & 9].
- The research work had been done on mainly eight areas of biomedical sciences. Molecular Biology, pharmacology, Virology and Microbiology were the basis of this research [vide table 3].
- The articles have been classified into various keywords and the word 'Human Coronavirus NL63' has been identified the most occurred keyword which was appeared in 10,033 times and placed in the first rank [vide

table7].

- The PubMed Central database is linguistically influenced by English language. Among 3539 articles, almost 3520 were written in English [vide table 4].

7. Conclusion

Based on PubMed Central database, the literature on Coronavirus disease research from 2010 to 2019 was analyzed using bibliometric methods. The number of publications on Coronavirus disease research indicated two clear peaks in the past one decade, on the time of SARS and MERS. Owing to global outbreak of COVID-19 a new extreme point of research was appeared in 2019. The research institutions are mainly from the USA and China and the universities are the most active institutions in scientific research.

The study has proved that an emerging epidemic is a powerful means for the generation of scientific knowledge. The study's findings have important implications for students, faculty, researchers and clinicians. The ranked journal list along with the subject and country list, serves as a clear reminder for necessary reading beyond one's favorite publications, even beyond one's own discipline, in order to discover the full range of scholarly literature on the topic.

Scientists still did not find out the accurate animal source or animal reservoir of Coronavirus infection. They are seeking the answer of the question that whether the SARS related influenza is a seasonal disease or not. The answers of these questions must help the biomedical field to prepare perfect antibody of the disease. The analysis results proved that at present in the absence of suitable drugs specifically aiming SARS-CoV-2, social isolation measures and rapid and accurate detection methods were developed.

Coronavirus disease will no doubt continue to attract the interest of researchers and clinicians across the spectrum of biomedical disciplines, leaving in its wake an ever expanding body of literature waiting to be explored.

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Journal of Indian Library Association: a bibliometric study during 2016-2020

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to examine the current trends of publication patterns in Library and Information Science research using bibliometric methods. To achieve the aim of the study, a popular national peer reviewed journals was selected i.e.' Journal of Indian Library Association' (JILA). During 2016-2020, total 22 issues and 129 articles were analyzed in various aspects such as distribution of articles, authorship patterns, state-wise contributors, most prolific author(s), and length of articles, subject-wise distribution of articles and number of keywords used. All collected data were presented in different tables and charts in systematic manner. The trends of authorship of articles are collaborative and most of the authors belong to Karnataka. Average length of articles is different and most of the papers have been written on 'bibliometric, webometric and scientometric analysis', users' study, library survey, LIS education, public library, information literacy etc during the study period.

Keywords : Bibliometric, ILA, JILA, Library and Information Science, Research trends.

1. Introduction

Biometric research is the statistical evaluation of bibliographic data, focusing on the analysis of citations of research findings and publications. In the past, bibliometric methods were used very often in the fields of Library and Information Science (LIS). Nowadays, it is trendy in all areas. It is used to provide a quantitative analysis of the academic literature. Many fields of research have used bibliometric to explore the impact of their field. Bibliometric is basically divided into two words, 'Biblio' stands for "Book" and 'Metrics' stands for "Measurement". We can now define Bibliometric as a method that includes statistical analysis of published articles and the citations published therein to

measure their impact.

Bibliometric is defined as "quantitative analysis of the characteristics, behaviours, and productivity of all aspects of written communication, librarians, and users of information" (Mahapatra, 2000, p. 4). The word bibliometric was introduced by Pritchard (1969), who replaced the earlier term "statistical bibliography" used for the same concept. Various bibliographic analysis techniques help to identify specific trends in the literature of a given field of study. Bibliometric studies are useful for evaluating library services, developing collections, finalizing policy, decision making, resource allocation and even weeding out of library resources.

The current study is a comparative bibliometric analysis during 2016-2020 of the 'Journal of Indian Library Association' (JILA) published by Indian Library Association (ILA). The journal is a peer reviewed journal that publishes the high quality research articles on LIS domain. The frequency of the journal is quarterly and it is UGC approved national level journal in India.

2. Review of literature

Several bibliometric analyses were conducted in recent past on national and international journals. Some of relevant works on the aforesaid subject are discussed here. Singh and Mishra (2013) analyzed 158 contributions of the IASLIC Bulletin during 2004-2010. The researcher carried out that most of the contribution is from academic institutions, majority of contributions (92) were 6 pages while majority of articles (95) were 1 to 10 citations. Total citations were 1600 from 158 articles. Kuriand Hajje (2014) examined the Citation Analysis of Pearl: A Journal of Library and Information Science during 2009-2011. They found that 1285 citations in 124 articles. They accounted 647 (50.35%) articles were written by single author, 288 (22.49) articles were written by two authors. Khan (2015) analysed 323 articles of Annals of Library and Information Studies (ALIS) for the period from 2004 to 2013 and he found 120 (37.15%) were contributed by single author while the rest of 203 (62.85%) were joint authors' contributions. The further study finds that most of the contributions were from India (87.31%). Mondal and Saha (2015) evaluated 115 articles of the Journal of Indian Library Association during 2008-2014 and found most of the authors belong to Delhi, average length of articles were 4-6 pages, maximum articles written on library automation, users' study and ICT related. Halder (2016) worked with the IASLIC Bulletin and Annals of

Library and Information Studies (ALIS) from the year 2010-2014. Researcher found that 115 articles were published in IASLIC Bulletin and 179 articles were published in ALIS during the above period. He distributed the research data in subject-wise, state-wise, country-wise and reference-wise. Kuri and Palled (2016) studied and analyzed the articles published in the Journal of Indian Library Association (JILA) during 2012 to 2014. He found that most of the articles published by single authors and maximum contributions were contributed from the Universities, i.e., 59 out of 119 articles. He also distributed research data in different tables and charts. Parameshwar (2016) analyzed 204 articles published during 2006-2015 in the IASLIC Bulletin. He found that highest publication published in 2010 (25 articles). Total 334 authors were contributed during the period and most of the articles were contributed by single authors 96 (46.08%), followed by two authors 90 (44.12%) and remaining 60 (9.80%) of the articles were written by three authors. Researcher presented the research data in many tables, i.e., state-wise, country-wise, length of articles, found prolific authors having 5 articles and also presented highly cited top ten papers. Brahma and Verma (2018) investigated 202 articles were published in Malaysian Journal of Library and Information Science (MJLIS) during 2007-2016 and found most of the contributor's, i.e., 31.17% from Malaysia, 2nd contributing country was India. They found 6285 references from 202 articles. Most of the articles were joint authorship (50.99%). Lijina (2018) evaluated the International Journal of Library and Information Science for a period 2012 to 2017 and found 161 articles were published during the period. In 2017, highest numbers of articles (54 articles) were published. The author also distributed research data in country-wise, state-wise, authorship pattern-

wise and explained. Raza and Malik (2018) done bibliometric study on Journal of Knowledge Management (JKM) and found 508 articles were contributed from 57 countries during 2009-2016. They also distributed the research data in different tables and graphs. Most significant out comes from their study that 307 articles were written on knowledge management. Prieto-Gutierrez and Segado-Boj (2019) analysed the research articles published in Annals of Library and Information Studies (ALIS), it is an India-based journal and the study was done during 2011- 2017. All collected data nicely distributed in various tables and charts.

3. Statement of the problem

After browsing through the published literatures on bibliometric studies on Indian LIS journals, it is observed that many researches have been conducted on bibliometric analysis and citation analysis on different period. The studied literatures have provided some important data to understand the recent trends in research on a specific subject domain. It is also observed that all collected data have been distributed in a very scientific manner. But at the same time the researchers found that during 2016 to 2020 no study has been conducted on 'Journal of Indian Library Association' (JILA) published by Indian Library Association (ILA). Regarding the journal's status in the field of LIS in India, the identified lacuna hinders the presentation of a comprehensive view on bibliometric study of Indian LIS journals. Thus the researchers have attempted to fill up the said lacuna by selecting the concerned study entitled as "Journal of Indian Library Association: a bibliometric study during 2016-2020".

4. Objectives of the study

The main objectives of the study are:

- To study issue-wise distribution of articles

- To examine authorship patterns of contributions
- To Find out state-wise distribution of contributions
- To know most prolific author
- To identify the length of articles
- To determine subject-wise distribution of the articles
- To find out number of keywords used
- To identify number of references used.

4. Scope of the study

The scope of the present study covers:

- Total 22 issues published in 'JILA' during 2016-2020
- Total 129 articles published in 'JILA' during 2016-2020
- The span of the study is limited to 5 years period i.e. 2016 to 2020 in JILA

5. Methodology

The relevant data to the study was downloaded from the official website of ILA (www.ilaindia.net/jila/index.php/jila/) from 2016-2020. Apart from that the relevant data had been collected from the different sources. A total of 129 articles written by 237 authors were traced from the 22 issues in this journal. The collected data were tabulated, classified, analysed using Microsoft Excel to meet the above-mentioned objectives.

6. Data analysis and interpretation

The present research work is a comparative bibliometric study of Journal of Indian Library Association (JILA) from the year 2016 to 2020. The research articles published during the period have been analyzed and distributed in different tables to fulfil the stated objectives.

6.1 Distribution of contributions

Table 1: Distribution of contributions in JILA

Year	Journal of Indian Library Association						
	Vol.	Issue				Total no of Articles	%
		1	2	3	4		
2016	52	7		5	5	17	13.18
2017	53	6	9		5	20	15.50
2018	54	6	5	6	6	23	17.83
2019	55	6	6	8	8	28	21.71
2020	56	9	8	11	13	41	31.78
Total	5	22				129	100

Table 1 shows that year-wise percentages of contributions are almost similar, although highest no. of articles published in JILA. The total contributions in five volumes in JILA were 129 with an

average of 25.8% articles published in a year. The maximum articles published in 2020 i.e. 41 (31.78%). However, least contributions were found in 2016, i.e., 17 (13.18%) and figure 1 clearly shows the year-wise growth.

Figure 1: Distribution of contributions in JILA

6.2 Authorship patterns

Table 2: Authorship patterns in JILA

JILA during 2016-2020			
No. of Author(s)	No of Articles	Total no. of author	%
One	45	45	18.98
Two	67	134	56.54
Three	10	30	12.65
Four	7	28	11.81
Total	129	237	100

In JILA, there were 237 personal authors contributed in 129 articles during five years. Table 2 demonstrates that most of the articles 67 (56.54%) written by joint authors in JILA and 45 articles that was 18.98% written by

single author. 10 articles were written by 3 authors and 7 articles written by more than three authors. Figure 2 has presented the distribution of the authorship pattern.

Figure 2: Authorship pattern of cited journals

6.3 State-wise contributions

Table 3: State-wise contribution in JILA

Sl.	State	JILA		
		No. of Contributors	%	Rank
1	Karnataka	45	18.98	1
2	Uttar Pradesh	37	15.61	2
3	New Delhi	26	10.97	3
4	Punjab	20	8.43	4
5	Maharashtra	17	7.14	5

Sl.	State	JILA		
		No. of Contributors	%	Rank
6	Mizoram	16	6.72	6
7	West Bengal	13	5.47	7
8	Haryana	12	5.04	8
9	Tamil Nadu	10	4.21	9
10	Madhya Pradesh	9	3.78	10
11	Jammu and Kashmir (Union Territory)	7	2.94	11
12	Kerala	5	2.10	12
13	Gujarat	4	1.68	13
14	Odisha	3	1.26	14
15	Puducherry (Union Territory)	2	0.84	15
16	Rajasthan	2	0.84	15
17	Uttarakhand	2	0.84	15
18	Arunachal Pradesh	1	0.42	16
19	Assam	1	0.42	16
20	Chhattisgarh	1	0.42	16
21	Jharkhand	1	0.42	16
22	Nagaland	1	0.42	16
23	Telangana	1	0.42	16
24	Iran(Other Country)	1	0.42	16
Total		237	100	

Previously it was mentioned that the national level journal is published from capital of India, i.e., New Delhi. As per table 3, most interesting result is found that highest contributed state is Karnataka (45 contributors, 18.98%) and 2nd highest state is

Uttar Pradesh (37 contributors). Whereas, New Delhi (26 contributors) is 3rd contributing state in JILA. Total 23 states and 1 foreign contributor have contributed in JILA during 2016 to 2020.

6.4 Rank-wise contributors**Table 4: Most prolific contributors in JILA during 2016-2020**

Authors	No. of articles	%	Round
Manoj Kumar Verma	5	2.100840336	2.1
B. D. Kumar	4	1.680672269	1.68
P.G. Prasad	3	1.260504202	1.26
Shailendra Kumar	3	1.260504202	1.26
Gururaj S.Hadagali	3	1.260504202	1.26
S. B. Dhawan	3	1.260504202	1.26
Shabhat Husain	3	1.260504202	1.26
B. M. Gupta	3	1.260504202	1.26
16 authors with two articles	32	13.44537815	13.45
178 authors having one article each	178	75.21008403	75.21
Total Authors	237	100	100

According to table 4 most prolific contributor in JILA is Manoj Kumar Verma. He has contributed 5 articles in JILA during study period. B. D. Kumar is the 2nd highest

contributor with 4 articles. 6 authors have contributed 3 articles each and 16 authors have contributed 2 research papers each and 178 authors have 1 article during 2016-2020.

6.5 Length of articles**Table 5 Length of articles in JILA during 2016-2020**

Sl. No.	No. of Pages	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	Total	Percentage	Mean
1	1--3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.60
2	4--6	5	6	8	1	0	20	15.50	
3	7--9	7	7	5	17	9	45	34.88	
4	10--12	1	5	9	8	19	42	32.55	
5	13--15	1	3	1	2	12	19	14.72	
6	16--18	0	0	2	0	1	3	2.32	
Total		14	21	23	28	41	129	100	

Table 5 describes the page-length of the published articles in JILA during 2016-2020. Out of 129 articles, topmost 45 articles (34.88%) have a length between 7-9 pages. The mean of page-length of 129 articles is 9.60.

6.6 Subject-wise distributions of the articles

The articles are categorised by subject-

wise and have been distributed in table 6. The subjects are selected considering the main 'keyword' of the articles published in JILA journals during the study period. All published articles have been divided into 18 subjects and found most of the articles are written on 'Bibliometrics and Scientometrics and Webometrics', i.e., 41 articles (31.78%) in JILA.

Table 6: Subject-wise distribution of articles published in JILA

Sl.No.	Subject	No.	% (Round of)
1	Bibliometrics / Scientometrics / Webometrics	41	31.78
2	Users studies	22	17.05
3	Library Survey	18	13.95
4	LIS Education/LIS Professionals/LIS Teachers	8	6.20
5	Public Library	4	3.10
6	Information Literacy	4	3.10
7	Library Services/Information Services	3	2.33
8	E-Resources	3	2.33
9	ICT and IT act.	3	2.33
10	Digital Libraries	2	1.55
11	Intellectual Property Right and Copy Right	2	1.55
12	Preservation and conservation	2	1.55
13	Academic Libraries	1	0.78
14	Library Resources	1	0.78
15	Library Automation	1	0.78
16	Collection Development	1	0.78
17	Marketing of LIS Services	1	0.78
18	Miscellaneous	12	9.30
Total no of articles		129	100.00

6.7 Numbers of keywords listed in articles**Table 7: Numbers of keywords used in each article**

No. of Keywords	Articles	Percentages
Nil	4	3.1
1--3	12	9.3
4--6	92	71.32
7--9	20	15.5
10--12	1	0.78
Total	129	100

Table 7 shows that the how many keywords used in each article during the study period in JILA. 4 to 6 (71.32%) keywords have been used in maximum articles, whereas 4 articles have been published without any key word.

6.8 Number of references listed in articles in JILA during 2016-2020**Table 8: No of references listed in JILA**

No. of References	Articles	Percentages (%)	Mean
1--5	8	6.2	14.35
6--10	34	26.36	
11--15	49	37.98	
16--20	18	13.95	
21--25	6	4.65	
26--30	4	3.1	
31--35	7	5.43	
35--40	3	2.33	
Total	129	100	

Table 8 shows that how many references have been used under each article. 49 articles (37.98%) used 11-15 no. of reference. Whereas mean of the references is 14.35.

Figure 3 will help to understand no. of reference used under the article during the study period.

Figure 3: No of reference listed in JILA

7. Findings

The main findings of the study during 2016-2020 in JILA are:

- Total 129 articles were published in 22 issues;
- 237 authors have contributed;
- Maximum articles, i.e., 67 have been published with joint author;
- Most of the articles, i.e., 45 have been contributed from the state of Karnataka;
- Most prolific contributor in JILA is Manoj Kumar Verma;
- Top most 45 articles (34.88%) have length between 7 to 9 pages;
- Most of the articles have been published on bibliometrics, scientometrics, webometrics and users' study;
- 92 (71.32%) articles are having 4-6 keywords;
- 49 (37.98%) articles have been used 11-15 number of references.

8. Conclusion

Bibliometric technique is being used for variety of purposes and even forecasting the potential of a particular domain. The Journal of Indian Library Association is publishing variety of articles for scholarly communication. Information in this journal is increasing gradually from year to year. Moreover, the findings of the study have highlighted multimodal bibliometric measures that would be helpful tool for all stakeholders to know the characteristic features of the journals. This kind of study also helps to find out the present research trends in LIS domain. Further study can be done on similar types of journals or study can be considered on another period of the same journal.

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